

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND ADHESION OF FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION (FFF) PRINTED BIOCOMPONENTS WITH CONTINUOUS VEGETABLE FIBER REINFORCEMENT

Natália V. dos Santos, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio), Brazil, nataliasvictoria@gmail.com

Daniel K. K. Cavalcanti, Federal Centre for Technological Education Celso Suckow da Fonseca (CEFET-RJ), Brazil, danielkkc@gmail.com

Jorge S. S. Neto, Federal Centre for Technological Education Celso Suckow da Fonseca (CEFET-RJ), Brazil, jorgesouzanetto@gmail.com

Mariana D. Banea, Federal Centre for Technological Education Celso Suckow da Fonseca (CEFET-RJ), Brazil, mdbanea@gmail.com

Daniel C. T. Cardoso, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio), Brazil, dctcardoso@puc-rio.br

ABSTRACT

In this research, continuous vegetable fibers are introduced as a reinforcing material to enhance the performance of FFF-printed biocomponents. This study investigates the interlaminar shear and structural response of printed biocomponents as well as its application in structural components through the manufacture of a printed truss. Results showed an increase in ILSS for flax fiber while reinforcements from yarns with larger diameters act as a defect in the composite, reducing its shear strength. Moreover, truss flexural tests demonstrated the feasibility of producing printed biocomponents with a maximum load variability of merely 3.43%.

KEYWORDS

Fused Filament Fabrication; Biocomposite; Vegetable fiber; Additive manufacturing.

INTRODUCTION

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is the modern manufacturing process where a computationally modeled 3D model data object is fabricated through overlapping layers (ASTM, 2021). This process starts with computationally modelling. This model is passed to a slicing program that separates the object into layers according to the appropriate print settings. This file is exported in .gcode format which is read by the printers. There are several types of materials used in 3D printing, such as metals, polymers, ceramics, and concrete. Among these materials, thermoplastic polymers, one of the most used materials in 3D printing, can be used by melting to acquire the determined shapes (Ngo et al., 2018). 3D printing of polymers is a constructive method with great potential for research in many fields, such as construction, biomedical, aerospace and even electronics (Manufacturing, 2021). The types of 3D printing polymers process present on the market includes extrusion, photopolymerization, powder bed fusion, material jetting, binder jetting, directed energy deposition and lamination (Goh et al., 2021).

Fiber reinforced 3D polymer printing becomes viable through extrusion, more specifically, by Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF). In FFF, the raw material filaments feed the printer by the stepper motor putting that filament into the cold-end which is responsible to limit the heat scape produced in the hot-end. The hotend is a heated nozzle that is programmed to heating the material to the melting point. The extruder moves along Cartesian axes and deposits the material on the printing table, which may or may not be heated. The layer-by-layer deposition process of additive manufacturing allows the use almost of the exact amount of material, significantly reducing waste.

The most used materials in printing extrusion are amorphous thermoplastic polymers (Turner et al., 2014), where acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polylactic acid (PLA) and Nylon are being the most

used (Borah, 2014). PLA is a biodegradable thermoplastic polymer of natural origin from renewable sources composed of lactic acid monomers from the microbial fermentation of ethanol from sugarcane (Galvão et al., 2017). Biodegradable polymers are often defined by polymers that suffer to photodegradation, oxidation and hydrolysis by microbially, generating chain scission and decomposing the material. This biodegradability contributes to the reduction of waste on the planet, allowing the material to decompose itself at the end of its useful life (Mohanty et al., 2005). However, due to its low mechanical properties, it is necessary to use some type of reinforcement in printing with PLA so it can be used in structural elements that are subject to mechanical stress. In this way and seeking to maintain the production of a biodegradable and natural composite, the choice of reinforcement becomes the use of vegetable fibers. Particularly, biocomposites with a combination of biodegradable polymer matrix and vegetable fiber can significantly reduce the carbon dioxide footprint due to their low density, biodegradability, and renewability (Badouard et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2014).

In view of this, this study aims to analyze the effects of the use of vegetable yarns in printed components through the analysis of interlaminar shear strength of the biocomposite and the structural response of a printed component.

MATERIALS

The jute, ramie, and sisal yarns were provided by SISAL SUL (São Paulo, Brazil), while flax yarn was provided by LKCWK (Fenggang, China). A 1.75mm diameter filament polylactic acid filament (PLA) provided by 3DLAB (Minas Gerais, Brazil) was used. Table 1 shows the main properties of the vegetable yarns.

Table 1: Properties of the vegetable yarns.

	Linear Density (g/m)	Diameter (mm)
Jute	0.31±0.05	0.52-1.17
Ramie	0.33±0.03	0.74-1.30
Sisal	1.80±0.05	1.39-2.01
Flax	0.10±0.01	0.28-0.44

PRINTING PROCESS

The PLA/Jute, PLA/Ramie, PLA/Flax and PLA/Sisal composites were manufactured by Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) using a Zmorph VX printer adapted for printing together polymer and continuous vegetable fiber yarns. Figure 1a shows a schematic drawing of the extruder configuration and in the Figure 1b the printer extruder can be seen. Table 2 shows the main printing parameters used in the biocomposite fabrication.

a) Schematic drawing.

b) Printer extruder.

Figure 1: Extruder printer of the composite schematic drawing and (b) printing process.

Table 2: Printing parameters.

Nozzle	2.1mm
Speed	10mm/s
Extruder temperature	200°C
Bed temperature	60°C
Layer height	1.5mm
Layer width	3.0mm

TEST METHODS

Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS)

The ILSS test was performed using the Instron® 5966 universal testing machine (Norwood, MA, USA) available in the Laboratory of Adhesives and Composites Materials (LADES) (CEFET/RJ, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil). The testing speed was 1 mm/min until failure and a load cell of 10 kN was used. Three specimens of each fiber were used for each composite type. The specimens were fabricated with two layers of height whereas the width was comprised of four rows. The span used was 20 mm. The tests were conducted at room temperature (23 °C) and 50% relative humidity. ASTM D2344 standard was used (ASTM, 2022). Figure 2 shows the printed specimen measure and the setup test. The fiber volume fraction of each composite is shown in Table 3.

a) Printed specimen. b) ILSS setup.

Figure 2: ILSS setup and printed specimen.

Table 3: Fiber volume fraction of the biocomposites.

	Fiber volume fraction (%)
PLA/Jute	10.80-18.30
PLA/Ramie	12.51-21.79
PLA/Sisal	34.33-48.16
PLA/Flax	1.63-3.32

Flexural test

The Flexural test was performed using the Instron® 23-100 universal testing machine (Norwood, MA, USA) available in the Laboratory of Structures and Materials (LEMDEC) (PUC-Rio, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil). The testing speed was 1 mm/min until failure and a load cell of 10 kN was used. Three printed truss reinforced with jute were tested using the printing parameters indicated in Printing Process and a continuous path code. The span used was 260 mm. The tests were conducted at room temperature (23 °C) and 50% relative humidity. ASTM D790 standard was used (ASTM, 2002). Figure 3a shows the printing process of the structural component, while Figure 3b shows the test setup.

a) Printing process. b) Flexural setup.

Figure 3: Development and flexural test of printed truss.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS)

Figure 4a shows the average ILSS test results of each reinforcement. It showed that the biocomposite reinforced with flax fiber yarn presented the best overall mechanical performance, with a load at break. Figure 4b shows the shear stressxstrain graph for each type of reinforcement. It was noted that, while biocomposites reinforced with flax showed a considerable increase in stiffness compared to neat-PLA, the other biocomposites exhibited a less accentuated slope than the polymer, demonstrating that the presence of these reinforcements reduce significantly the bond between layers of the material (Cavalcanti et al., 2022).

Figure 4: Interlaminar shear strength results.

Table 4 presents a summary of the ILSS test, where the average values of resistance, standard deviation and coefficient of variation for Neat-PLA and for biocomposites were observed. Analyzing the results, it appears that the flax-reinforced composites were the only ones to present an improvement of 0.94% in the interlaminar shear strength of the specimens when compared to Neat-PLA. The other biocomposites showed a decrease in resistance compared to the pure polymer, with a maximum reduction value of 20.87% in the case of the composite reinforced with sisal fiber yarn. This hydrophobic characteristic further complicates the process of matrix impregnation within the yarn of significant diameter.

Table 4: Values of ILSS properties obtained.

	ILSS (MPa)	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
PLA	8.53	0.09	1.11%
PLA/Jute	6.92	0.17	2.46%
PLA/Ramie	7.64	0.28	8.94%
PLA/Sisal	6.75	0.60	6.86%
PLA/Flax	8.61	0.60	7.01%

All components exhibited rupture under flexural tension. As depicted in Figure 5a, the fiber retained its structural integrity, even in the presence of matrix cracking, effectively bearing a portion of the applied

load and forming bridging between cracks. Although the failure mode of the specimens was characterized as flexural tensile in nature, according to the ASTM D2344 Standard, the interlaminar shear strength could still be determined (ASTM, 2022). Additionally, Figure 5b shows the presence of microcracks on the tensioned side of the specimen. The observed phenomenon can likely be attributed to inadequate interfacial adhesion between the fiber and the matrix, primarily stemming from the hydrophobic nature of the fiber (Lopes et al., 2010).

a) Specimen main crack with intact yarn. b) Microcracks in the matrix.

Figure 5: Failure modes in ILSS test.

Flexural truss test

Through the flexural testing of the printed truss, it was feasible to acquire data regarding the maximum strength and failure modes exhibited by the printed component, as depicted in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The results indicate that there was no substantial variance observed in the structural behavior and rigidity among the tested samples. In all instances, the failure occurred suddenly and abruptly. Upon preliminary analysis of the printed structural components, it was observed that, despite the inherent variability associated with vegetable fibers, the maximum failure exhibited a minimal variation of merely 3.43%.

Figure 6: Force vs Displacement of the printed truss.

Every truss experienced a failure mode similar to the one depicted in Figure 7a. The initiation of rupture consistently occurred at the same location (Figure 7b), attributed to shear stress exerted on the printing curve at the truss node point. Furthermore, shear failure was observed (Figure 7c), where the shear failure ran interlaminarly until it broke the subsequent layers. These issues could potentially be mitigated by incorporating interlayers with varied fiber orientations, strategically positioned to minimize such failure mechanisms.

a) Printed truss failure

b) Shear failure in the printing curve

c) Shear failure in the upper flange

Figure 7: Failure modes of the truss.

CONCLUSION

This study presents and discusses the impact of employing continuous vegetable fibers as reinforcement for fused filament fabrication (FFF) printed biocomposites. The utilization of natural fibers as a reinforcing agent in the long-form truss manufactured via additive manufacturing has displayed promising results. Despite the reduction in interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) properties by up to 20.87%, the maximum applied force on the truss exhibited only a 3.43% variation. This finding demonstrates the feasibility of employing vegetable fibers in components necessitating property control. As such, most of the fibers acted as fillers, reducing the amount of thermoplastic used in up to 48.20%, further reducing the ecological footprint of the biocomposite. This study contributes to the ongoing advancements in additive manufacturing, specifically in the field of biocompatible materials, by providing insights into the utilization of continuous vegetable fibers for enhanced performance and functionality of FFF-printed biocomponents.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All testing was conducted at the Laboratory of Structures and Materials of the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro and at the Laboratory of Adhesives and Composite Materials of CEFET-Rio. This study was financed in part by the *Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior* – Brazil (CAPES) – Finance Code 001 and by Brazilian funding agencies FAPERJ and CNPq. This project was also supported by the State Institute of Engineering and Architecture (IEEA), linked to the State Department of Infrastructure of the State of Rio de Janeiro, through Contract 001/2021 with resources from the Government of the State of Rio de Janeiro.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

1. All necessary data is presented in this paper.

CITATIONS

ASTM. (2002). ASTM D790 - Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials. In *Annual Book of ASTM Standards* (pp. 1–12). <https://doi.org/10.1520/D0790-15E02>.

ASTM. (2021). *ASTM 52900 Additive manufacturing - General principles - Terminology*.

ASTM. (2022). *ASTM D2344 - Short Beam Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials and Their Laminates*.

Badouard, C., Traon, F., Denoual, C., Mayer-Laigle, C., Paës, G., & Bourmaud, A. (2019). Exploring mechanical properties of fully compostable flax reinforced composite filaments for 3D printing applications. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 135(December 2018), 246–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2019.04.049>

Borah, S. (2014). 3D Printer Filament Length Monitor. *International Journal of Science, Technology and Society*, 2(5), 129. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijsts.20140205.16>

Cavalcanti, D. K. K., Neto, J. S. S., Queiroz, H. F. M. d., Wu, Y., Neto, V. F. S., & Banea, M. D. (2022). Development and Mechanical Characterization of Short Curauá Fiber-Reinforced PLA Composites Made via Fused Deposition Modeling. *Polymers*, 14(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14225047>

Galvão, A. C. F., Poppe, M. K., Bressan Rocha, B., Durieux, L., Nogueira, L. A. H., & Macedo, I. C. (2017). *Second-generation sugarcane bioenergy & biochemicals*.

Goh, G. D., Sing, S. L., & Yeong, W. Y. (2021). A review on machine learning in 3D printing: applications, potential, and challenges. In *Artificial Intelligence Review* (Vol. 54, Issue 1). Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-020-09876-9>

Lopes, F. F. M., Araújo, G. T. de, Nascimento, J. W. B. do, Gadelha, T. S., & Silva, V. R. da. (2010). Study of the effects of acetylation treatments on sisal fiber. *Revista Brasileira de Engenharia Agrícola e Ambiental*, 14(7), 783–788. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1415-43662010000700015>

Manufacturing, A. (2021). *Process – Structure – Properties in Polymer*. 13–14.

Mohanty, A. K., Misra, M., & Drzal, L. T. (2005). NATURAL FIBERS, BIOPOLYMERS, AND BIOCOMPOSITES. In *Natural Fibers, Biopolymers, and Biocomposites*.

Ngo, T. D., Kashani, A., Imbalzano, G., Nguyen, K. T. Q., & Hui, D. (2018). Additive manufacturing (3D printing): A review of materials, methods, applications and challenges. *Composites Part B: Composites for Engineering*, 163, 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.08.028>

Engineering, 143(February), 172–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.02.012>

Turner, B. N., Strong, R., & Gold, S. A. (2014). A review of melt extrusion additive manufacturing processes: I. Process design and modeling. *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, 20(3), 192–204. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RPJ-01-2013-0012>

Wang, K., Addiego, F., Laachachi, A., Kaouache, B., Bahlouli, N., Toniazzi, V., & Ruch, D. (2014). Dynamic behavior and flame retardancy of HDPE/hemp short fiber composites: Effect of coupling agent and fiber loading. *Composite Structures*, 113(1), 74–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.03.009>